

Observation and Stabilization of LTV Systems With Time-Varying Measurement Delay [★]

Ricardo Sanz ^a, Pedro García ^a, Miroslav Krstic ^b

^a*Department of Systems Engineering and Automation, Universitat Politècnica de València, 46022 València, Spain*

^b*Dept. of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, University of California San Diego, La Jolla, CA 92093-0411, USA*

Abstract

This work deals with observer-based output-feedback stabilization of linear time-varying (LTV) systems with time-varying measurement delay. The delay is modeled by a first-order hyperbolic partial differential equation (PDE), whose boundary condition evolves according to an ordinary differential equation (ODE), namely, the plant. The overall system is thus represented by an ODE-PDE cascade, which is also the structure of the proposed observer. The exponential stability of the estimation error is established for arbitrarily large time-varying delays. An observer-based controller is also introduced and the closed-loop stability is proved. The separation principle holds and the design of both the observer and controller gains can be done as if there was no delay. Some simulations illustrate the feasibility of this approach.

Key words: time-varying plants, state observer; output feedback; time-varying delays; PDEs.

1 Introduction

The state estimation problem in the presence of delayed measurements is ubiquitous in engineering applications and it has attracted attention over the past decades Watanabe and Ito (1981); Klamka (1982); de Souza et al. (2001); Germani et al. (2002); Fridman et al. (2003); Krstic and Smyshlyaev (2008). The problem of stabilizing an LTV system is also of interest in practice, as it arises in trajectory tracking of nonlinear systems Rugh and Shamma (2000). See Zhou (2016) for recent results on stability of LTV systems. Only a few works have been reported in which LTV systems with measurement delay are considered Pila et al. (1999); Basin et al. (2010); Song et al. (2017)

As shown in Krstic and Smyshlyaev (2008); Nicaise et al. (2009), time-delay systems can be modeled as the interconnection of an ODE (plant dynamics) and a first-order hyperbolic PDE (delay dynamics). In this framework, the approach consists of finding an invertible backstepping transformation that maps the ODE-PDE cascade

into an exponentially stable target system Smyshlyaev and Krstic (2004, 2005). This methodology has been shown to be very useful when dealing with time-delay systems, providing rigorous tools for analysis and design, which have been exploited in many ways Krstic (2009, 2010b); Bresch-Pietri and Krstic (2014); Ahmed-Ali et al. (2018); Sanz et al. (2018). A tutorial on compensating infinite-dimensional actuator and sensor dynamics is given in Krstic (2010a). When applied to input-delay systems, the backstepping approach has led to predictor-based controllers, equivalent to those early derived in Manitius and Olbrot (1979); Kwon and Pearson (1980); Artstein (1982). However, when applied to systems with measurement delays, the resulting observer is substantially different (see Remarks 4-7 in Krstic and Smyshlyaev (2008) for a discussion) from those originally proposed in Watanabe and Ito (1981); Klamka (1982), which involved distributed integral terms.

In the context of systems with measurement delays, a common approach consist of using a conventional observer structure and then estimating upper bounds on the admissible delay, for which powerful techniques are available de Souza et al. (2001); Fridman et al. (2003); Zhang and Han (2008); see also the monograph Fridman (2014). A different strategy consists of proposing new observers that specifically handle the delay. Early results were based on estimating a delayed state and then pro-

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Email addresses: risanda@upv.es (Ricardo Sanz), pggil@ai2.upv.es (Pedro García), krstic@ucsd.edu (Miroslav Krstic).

jecting it ahead via an state predictor Watanabe and Ito (1981); Klamka (1982). This approach can be also applied when the delay is time-varying, see Section 6.3 in Krstic (2009). In Pila et al. (1999), an H_∞ filter is derived for LTV systems with constant measurement delay. However, these approaches need the online computation of a distributed integral over the past control actions, whose approximation may lead to instability Van Assche et al. (1999); Zhong (2004). A new approach for state observation with long constant delays was introduced in Germani et al. (2002), where a chain of observers was employed. The idea is that each of the observers in the chain is in charge of predicting the system state over a fraction of the total delay. This novel idea has been also extended to time-varying delays Cacace et al. (2014); Cacace and Germani (2017). A different technique was used in Zhou et al. (2013), based on a truncated predictor that neglects the integral term. A novel observer with an ODE-PDE cascade structure was introduced in Krstic and Smyshlyaev (2008), as mentioned above, which handled arbitrarily large constant delays. Among the aforementioned works, only Pila et al. (1999) considers LTV systems. Other related works include: Mazenc and Malisoff (2017), where a predictor for LTV systems with time-varying input delays was proposed; Selivanov and Fridman (2016), where an observer-based predictor for network-based control was designed using reduction approach; and Cacace et al. (2010), where an observer was designed for nonlinear systems with sufficiently small unknown time-varying delays.

In this paper, a generalization of the observer derived in Krstic and Smyshlyaev (2008) is proposed, with a twofold contribution. On one hand, time-varying delays are considered and, on the other hand, the observer is also adapted to deal with LTV systems. The open-loop plant is allowed to contain exponentially unstable modes and arbitrarily large time-varying delays can be handled. To the best of the author's knowledge, this is a departure from previous works, even for LTI systems. Furthermore, the proposed observer is used to derive an exponentially stabilizing output-feedback controller for LTI/LTV systems with time-varying measurement delay.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Some preliminaries about LTV systems and the PDE representation of the delay are given in Section 2. The proposed observer is introduced in Section 3, where the exponential stability of the estimation error is established. An observer-based controller is proposed in Section 4, where the closed-loop stability is proved. The feasibility of this strategy is illustrated with an example in Section 5.

Notation: The 2-norm of a finite-dimensional vector and the corresponding induced matrix norm are denoted by $|\cdot|$. The L_p -norm of matrix (or vector) function $X(t) : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ denoted by $\|X\|_p = (\int_a^b |X(s)|^p ds)^{1/p}$, with the particular case $\|X\|_\infty = \text{ess sup}_{s \in [a, b]} |X(s)|$. A

function is said to belong to the space $L_p([a, b])$ if it has a finite L_p -norm.

2 Preliminaries

Consider the following LTV system with measurement delay

$$\dot{X}(t) = A(t)X(t) + B(t)U(t), \quad (1)$$

$$Y(t) = C(\phi(t))X(\phi(t)), \quad (2)$$

$$X(\theta) = X_0(\theta), \quad \forall \theta \in [\phi(t_0), t_0], \quad (3)$$

where $X(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the state, $U(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the control action, the system matrices $A : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $B : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ and $C : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{q \times n}$ are piecewise-continuous uniformly-bounded functions, $\phi : \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{> 0}$ is a continuously differentiable function that incorporates the measurement delay, $X_0 : [\phi(t_0), t_0] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ denotes the initial condition and $t_0 \geq 0$ is the initial time.

Assumption 1 *The delay function ϕ is known, continuously differentiable and there exist $\underline{D}, \overline{D}, c_1, c_2 > 0$ such that*

$$\underline{D} \leq t - \phi(t) \leq \overline{D},$$

and

$$c_1 \leq \dot{\phi}(t) \leq c_2,$$

hold for all $t \geq 0$.

Assumption 2 *There exists a time-varying matrix function $L : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times q}$ such that the origin of $\dot{\mathcal{X}}(t) = (A(t) - L(t)C(t))\mathcal{X}(t)$ is uniformly exponentially stable for all $t \geq \phi(t_0)$. In other words, there exist positive definite, bounded, symmetric, time-varying matrices $W_1(t), Q_1(t) : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ such that $\dot{W}_1(t) + W_1(t)F_1(t) + F_1^T(t)W_1(t) \leq -Q_1(t)$, $\forall t \geq \phi(t_0)$, where $F_1(t) = A(t) - L(t)C(t)$.*

The function $\phi(t)$ can be expressed as $\phi(t) = t - D(t)$, where $D : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{> 0}$ is the measurement delay. Since both c_2 and \overline{D} are allowed to be arbitrarily large, the main limitations imposed by Assumption 1 are $\dot{D}(t) < 1$ and $D(t) > 0$. The former is a common assumption when dealing with time-varying delays Zhou et al. (2013); Mazenc and Malisoff (2017); while the latter has to do with the PDE representation of the delay, in which the propagation speed becomes infinity if the delay is zero Krstic (2010b). The delay is then considered to be sort of slowly-varying (it can decrease arbitrarily fast but it can only increase at a rate smaller than one). This is a sufficient condition to ensure the invertibility of $\phi(t)$, which, in turn, seems to be a fundamental requirement if compensation of large time-varying delays is pursued. The constraint of the delay being not null is less restrictive as it can be easily avoided (see Remark 10). On the other hand, Assumption 2 is needed in the subsequent

analysis to guarantee the stabilization of the LTV system.

Recall that any solution of the homogeneous equation $\dot{X}(t) = A(t)X(t)$ can be written as $X(t) = \Phi(t, t_0)X(t_0)$, where

$$\Phi(t, t_0) = P(t)P^{-1}(t_0), \quad (4)$$

is the so-called state transition matrix, and $P : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the solution of the matrix initial value problem $\dot{P}(t) = A(t)P(t)$, $P(0) = I$. The methodology developed in this paper is based on representing the time-varying measurement delay as a transport phenomenon, which is modeled by a first-order hyperbolic PDE. Similarly to Krstic (2010b), let us introduce the state for the transport equation $u : [0, 1] \times \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^q$, defined by

$$u(x, t) = C(\varphi(x, t))X(\varphi(x, t)), \quad \forall x \in [0, 1], \quad (5)$$

where

$$\varphi(x, t) = \phi(t) + x(t - \phi(t)), \quad (6)$$

leading to the boundary values $u(0, t) = Y(t)$ and $u(1, t) = C(t)X(t)$. The system (1)-(2) can be then represented by the following ODE-PDE cascade

$$\dot{X}(t) = A(t)X(t) + B(t)U(t), \quad (7)$$

$$u_t(x, t) = \pi(x, t)u_x(x, t), \quad (8)$$

$$u(1, 0) = C(t)X(t), \quad (9)$$

$$Y(t) = u(0, t), \quad (10)$$

with

$$\pi(x, t) = \frac{\dot{\phi}(t) + x(1 - \dot{\phi}(t))}{t - \phi(t)}. \quad (11)$$

3 Proposed observer

The main result is stated in the following theorem. Note that, for the sake of clarity, in what follows $\varphi(x, t)$ and $\phi(t)$ are often denoted simply by φ and ϕ , respectively.

Theorem 3 *Given (7)-(10), the observer*

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\hat{X}}(t) &= A(t)\hat{X}(t) + B(t)U(t) \\ &\quad + \dot{\phi}(t)\Phi(t, \phi)L(\phi)(Y(t) - \hat{u}(0, t)), \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{u}_t(x, t) &= \pi(x, t)\hat{u}_x(x, t) \\ &\quad + \dot{\phi}(t)C(\varphi)\Phi(\varphi, \phi)L(\phi)(Y(t) - \hat{u}(0, t)), \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

$$\hat{u}(1, 0) = C(t)\hat{X}(t). \quad (14)$$

is uniformly exponentially convergent, in the sense that, there exist $M, \mu > 0$, such that $\Upsilon(t) \leq M\Upsilon(t_0)e^{-\mu(t-t_0)}$, $\forall t \geq t_0 \geq 0$, where

$$\Upsilon(t) = |X(t) - \hat{X}(t)|^2 + \int_0^1 |u(x, t) - \hat{u}(x, t)|^2 dx.$$

PROOF. See Appendix A.

Corollary 4 *For an LTI system, that is, with $A(t) = A$, $B(t) = B$ and $C(t) = C$, the observer*

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\hat{X}}(t) &= A\hat{X}(t) + BU(t) \\ &\quad + \dot{\phi}(t)e^{A(t-\phi(t))}L(Y(t) - \hat{u}(0, t)), \\ \hat{u}_t(x, t) &= \pi(x, t)\hat{u}_x(x, t) \\ &\quad + C\dot{\phi}(t)e^{Ax(t-\phi(t))}L(Y(t) - \hat{u}(0, t)), \\ \hat{u}(1, t) &= C\hat{X}(t), \end{aligned}$$

where L is chosen such that $A-LC$ is Hurwitz, guarantees that \hat{X}, \hat{u} exponentially converge to X, u , in the sense that, there exist $M, \mu > 0$, such that $\Upsilon(t) \leq M\Upsilon(0)e^{-\mu t}$, $\forall t \geq 0$.

PROOF. The state transition matrix of an LTI system is given by $\Phi(t, t_0) = e^{A(t-t_0)}$. Then, one has that $\Phi(t, \phi) = e^{A(t-\phi(t))}$, $\Phi(\varphi, \phi) = e^{A\varphi(t-\phi(t))}$ and thus the corollary follows from Theorem 3. \square

Remark 5 Notice that the PDE observer state is nothing but $u(x, t) = Y(\phi^{-1}(\varphi(x, t)))$, which can be seen from (2) and (5). Defining $\tilde{Y}(\phi^{-1}(\varphi(x, t))) = \hat{u}(x, t)$, $\tilde{Y}(t) = Y(t) - \hat{Y}(t)$ and using the change of variable $s = \phi^{-1}(\varphi(x, t))$, one can rewrite $\Upsilon(t)$ as

$$\Upsilon(t) = |\tilde{X}(t)|^2 + \frac{1}{D(t)} \int_t^{\phi^{-1}(t)} |\tilde{Y}(s)|^2 \dot{\phi}(s) ds.$$

The latter points out the fact that the proposed observer produces an exponentially convergent prediction of the output over the time window $[t, \phi^{-1}(t)]$, $\forall t \geq t_0$.

Remark 6 One may argue that, if the delay is continuous and known and hence the measurement $C(X - \bar{D})X(t - \bar{D})$ is always available for all $t \geq \bar{D}$, then the problem can be treated by considering a constant maximum delay. However, this methodology is not efficient in general, provided that the “freshest” information of the output has to be intentionally delayed. This strategy is employed in Cacace and Germani (2017) for LTI systems. The estimate of the delayed state is then advanced by means of a chain of predictors. However, the artificially delayed output requires the explicit inverse of the delay function. Furthermore, in the design process, an integral of a matrix norm needs to be computed therein to determine the number of elements in the chain.

Remark 7 Also, one can approach this problem by designing a delayed observer to estimate $X(\phi(t))$ and then advancing it $\phi^{-1}(t)$ units of time ahead using a time-varying predictor, as it was done in Section V in Krstic

(2010b) for LTI systems with time-varying delay. However, that predictor needs the inverse of the delay function explicitly and it involves the computation of a distributed integral. Recall that even predictors for LTI systems with constant delay exhibit numerical issues Mondié and Michiels (2003); Zhong (2004); Karafyllis and Krstic (2017).

4 Application to control

The following assumption is needed, which is the counterpart of Assumption 2, for control purposes.

Assumption 8 *There exists a time-varying matrix function $K : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ such that the origin of $\dot{X}(t) = (A(t) + B(t)K(t))X(t)$ is uniformly exponentially stable for all $t \geq t_0$. In other words, there exist positive definite, bounded, symmetric, time-varying matrices $W_2(t), Q_2(t) : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ such that $\dot{W}_2(t) + W_2(t)F_2(t) + F_2(t)^T W_2(t) \leq -Q_2(t), \forall t \geq t_0$, where $F_2(t) = A(t) + B(t)K(t)$.*

Theorem 9 *The closed-loop composed of the system (1)-(2), the observer (12)-(14) and the control law*

$$U(t) = K(t)\hat{X}(t), \quad (15)$$

is uniformly exponentially stable in the sense that, there exist $R, \rho > 0$ such that for all initial conditions $(X_0(\cdot), \hat{X}_0, \hat{u}_0(\cdot, t_0)) \in L_2(\phi(t_0), t_0) \times \mathbb{R}^n \times L_2(0, 1)$, the following holds $\Gamma(t) \leq R\Gamma(t_0)e^{-\rho(t-t_0)}$, where

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma(t) = & |X(t)|^2 + \frac{1}{D(t)} \int_{\phi(t)}^t |C(\theta)X(\theta)|^2 d\theta \\ & + |\hat{X}(t)|^2 + \int_0^1 \hat{u}(x, t)^2 dx. \end{aligned}$$

PROOF. Let us plug (15) into (1) and use (A.1) and (A.34) to obtain

$$\dot{X}(t) = F_2(t)X(t) - B(t)K(t)\Phi(t, \phi(t))\tilde{Z}(t). \quad (16)$$

Let us consider $L_1(t) = \gamma \int_0^1 e^{bx}|u(x, t)|^2 dx$, with $\gamma > 0$. Using similar arguments to those in the proof of Theorem 4, the derivative of $L_1(t)$ along the trajectories of (7)-(9) can be bounded by

$$\dot{L}_1(t) \leq \gamma e^b \underline{D} \|C\|_\infty^2 |X|^2 - \frac{\gamma \beta^*}{\overline{D}} \int_0^1 e^{bx}|u(x, t)|^2 dx \quad (17)$$

Now, let us consider also $L_2(t) = \kappa X(t)^T W_2(t) X(t)$ with $\kappa > 0$, whose derivative along (16) can be bounded by

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{L}_2(t) & \leq -\kappa q_2 |X|^2 + 2\kappa |X^T W_2 B K \Phi(t, \phi) \tilde{Z}| \\ & \leq -\frac{\kappa q_2}{2} |X|^2 + \frac{2\kappa \tau_2^2}{q_2} |\tilde{Z}|^2, \quad \forall t \geq t_0, \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where $\tau_2 = \|W_2(t)B(t)K(t)\Phi(t, \phi(t))\|_\infty$ and Assumption (8) was used, which implies the existence of a $q_2 > 0$ such that $Q_2(t) \geq q_2 I, \forall t \geq t_0$. Defining $L_0(t) = L_1(t) + L_2(t)$, using (17)-(18) and choosing $\gamma = \kappa q_2 / (4e^b \underline{D} \|C\|_\infty^2)$, yields

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{L}_0(t) & \leq -\frac{\kappa q_2}{4} |X|^2 + \frac{2\kappa \tau_2^2}{q_2} |\tilde{Z}|^2 \\ & \quad - \frac{\gamma \beta^*}{\overline{D}} \int_0^1 e^{bx}|u(x, t)|^2 dx, \quad \forall t \geq t_0. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Now, let us choose the a composite Lyapunov function $\mathcal{V}(t) = L_0(t) + V_0(t)$, whose derivative can be bounded, using (A.30) and (19), and selecting $\kappa = c_1 q_1 q_2 / (8\tau_2^2)$, by

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathcal{V}}(t) & \leq -\frac{\kappa q_2}{4} |X|^2 - \frac{c_1 q_1}{4} |\tilde{Z}|^2 - \frac{\gamma \beta^*}{\overline{D}} \int_0^1 e^{bx}|u(x, t)|^2 dx \\ & \quad - \frac{2\beta^* c_2^2 \tau_1^2}{c_1^2 q_1} \int_0^1 e^{bx} \tilde{w}^2(x, t) dx. \end{aligned}$$

Then $\dot{\mathcal{V}}(t) \leq -\rho \mathcal{V}(t), \forall t \geq t_0$ and an exponential stability estimate $\mathcal{V}(t) \leq e^{-\rho(t-t_0)} \mathcal{V}(t_0), \forall t \geq t_0$, in terms of $(X, \tilde{Z}, u, \tilde{w})$, is established. Proceeding as in the proof of Theorem 2, this estimate can be related to the original variables $(X, \tilde{X}, u, \tilde{u})$ using the inverse transformation (A.34)-(A.35) and then to (X, \hat{X}, u, \hat{u}) using (A.1)-(A.2), leading to $\Gamma(t) \leq R\Gamma(t_0)e^{-\rho(t-t_0)}, \forall t \geq 0$, with $\Gamma(t) = |X(t)|^2 + \int_0^1 |u(x, t)|^2 dx + |\hat{X}(t)|^2 + \int_0^1 |\hat{u}(x, t)|^2 dx$. This is omitted here for brevity. Finally, introducing (5) into $\Gamma(t)$ and performing the change of variable $\theta = \varphi(x, t)$ completes the proof. \square

5 Simulations

Let us consider (1)-(2) with $A(t) = (2 + t^2)/(1 + t^2)$, $\phi(t) = t - D(t)$ and $D(t) = 1 + 0.5 \sin t$. Note that $A : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [2, 1)$, and thus the open-loop system is potentially unstable. The control of such a system is challenging, even for constant delay and constant coefficients Middleton and Miller (2007). Since $\dot{\phi}(t) = 1 + 0.5 \cos t$, Assumption 1 is satisfied with $\underline{D} = 0.5, \overline{D} = 1.5, c_1 = 0.5$ and $c_2 = 1.5$. It is readily verified that $P(t) = e^{t+\text{atan}t}$ is a fundamental matrix and thus $\Phi(t, t_0) =$

Fig. 1. Simulation results. Actual state, estimated state and output (top); control action (center); time-varying delay (bottom)

$e^{t-t_0+atan t-atan t_0}$. Choosing $W_1(t) = W_2(t) = 1/2$, Assumptions 2 and 7 are fulfilled with any $L > \|A\|_\infty$ and any $K < \|A\|_\infty$, respectively, and thus the gains are selected as $L = -K = 2$. The initial time is set to $t_0 = 0$ and the initial condition is arbitrary chosen as $X_0(\theta) = 0, \forall \theta \in [\phi(0), 0)$, $X_0(0) = 1$. The control law (15) with the observer (12)-(14) is implemented, where

$$\pi(x, t) = \frac{1 + (1 - x)0.5 \cos t}{1 - 0.5 \sin t}. \quad (20)$$

A first-order approximation both in time (Δt) and space (Δx) is used for the discretization. The so-called Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) condition, $\Delta x > \Delta t \sup_{x,t} |\pi(x, t)|$, must hold in order to guarantee numerical stability. The time step is arbitrarily selected as $\Delta t = 0.005$ s and thus $\Delta x = 0.015$, provided that the bound $\sup_{x,t} |\pi(x, t)| \leq 3$ is easily obtained from (20).

The simulation results are shown in Fig. 1. One can see how the system runs in open-loop over a period of time, during which there is no measurable information about the system (see dotted line). The exact time can be computed by solving $\phi(t) = 0$ for $t \geq 0$, which yields $t \approx 1.5$. After that, one can see how the estimated state (dashed) converges to the actual one (full), which in turn, is driven exponentially to zero. The control action and the time-varying delay are also depicted in the central and bottom plots, respectively.

Remark 10 *The computation of $\pi(x, t)$ involves the inverse of $D(t) = t - \phi(t)$ and thus the delay is not allowed to be zero, as indicated by Assumption 1. This issue can be avoided in practice by considering a minimum threshold, D_{th} when computing $\pi(x, t)$ so that, when $D(t) < D_{th}$, then $\pi(x, t) = (\dot{\phi}(t) + x(1 - \dot{\phi}(t)))/D_{th}$. This has been tested with the example above, modifying the delay func-*

tion as $D(t) = 0.5 - 0.5 \sin t$, which vanishes at some time instants. Implementing the threshold strategy with $D_{th} = 0.01$ leads to satisfactory results.

6 Conclusions

A new strategy to control exponentially unstable LTV systems with arbitrarily large time-varying measurement delay has been introduced. The controller is based on a novel observer with an ODE-PDE cascade structure, which is a generalization of a previously reported one, applicable only to constant delays. The feasibility of this approach is demonstrated in simulations with a challenging example. Future work may consist in extending this results to derive an observer-based controller for LTV systems with arbitrarily large input and output time-varying delays. Some preliminary investigations show that the observer derived in this work may be a cornerstone to that end. This work might be also extended to consider uncertainties in the system matrices and/or the time-delay. This could be achieved by means of the reduction approach, as one of the reviewers suggested.

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References

- Ahmed-Ali, T., Giri, F., Krstic, M., and Kahelras, M. (2018). PDE based observer design for nonlinear systems with large output delay. *Systems & Control Letters*, 113:1–8.
- Artstein, Z. (1982). Linear systems with delayed controls: A reduction. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, 27(4):869–879.
- Basin, M., Shi, P., and Calderon-Alvarez, D. (2010). Central suboptimal H_∞ filter design for linear time-varying systems with state and measurement delays. *International Journal of Systems Science*, 41(4):411–421.
- Bresch-Pietri, D. and Krstic, M. (2014). Delay-adaptive control for nonlinear systems. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, 59(5):1203–1218.
- Cacace, F. and Germani, A. (2017). Output feedback control of linear systems with input, state and output delays by chains of predictors. *Automatica*, 85:455–461.
- Cacace, F., Germani, A., and Manes, C. (2010). An observer for a class of nonlinear systems with time-varying observation delay. *Systems & Control Letters*, 59(5):305–312.

- Cacace, F., Germani, A., and Manes, C. (2014). Predictor-based control of linear systems with large and variable measurement delays. *International Journal of Control*, 87(4):704–714.
- de Souza, C. E., Palhares, R. M., and Peres, P. D. (2001). Robust H_∞ design for uncertain linear systems with multiple time-varying state delays. *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, 49(3):569–576.
- Fridman, E. (2014). *Introduction to time-delay systems: Analysis and control*. Springer.
- Fridman, E., Shaked, U., and Xie, L. (2003). Robust H_∞ filtering of linear systems with time-varying delay. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, 48(1):159–165.
- Germani, A., Manes, C., and Pepe, P. (2002). A new approach to state observation of nonlinear systems with delayed output. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, 47(1):96–101.
- Karafyllis, I. and Krstic, M. (2017). *Predictor feedback for delay systems: Implementations and approximations*. Springer.
- Klamka, J. (1982). Observer for linear feedback control of systems with distributed delays in controls and outputs. *Systems & Control Letters*, 1(5):326–331.
- Krstic, M. (2009). *Delay compensation for nonlinear, adaptive, and PDE systems*. Springer.
- Krstic, M. (2010a). Compensation of infinite-dimensional actuator and sensor dynamics. *IEEE Control Systems*, 30(1):22–41.
- Krstic, M. (2010b). Lyapunov stability of linear predictor feedback for time-varying input delay. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, 55(2):554–559.
- Krstic, M. and Smyshlyaev, A. (2008). Backstepping boundary control for first-order hyperbolic PDEs and application to systems with actuator and sensor delays. *Systems & Control Letters*, 57(9):750–758.
- Kwon, W. and Pearson, A. (1980). Feedback stabilization of linear systems with delayed control. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic control*, 25(2):266–269.
- Manitius, A. and Olbrot, A. (1979). Finite spectrum assignment problem for systems with delays. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, 24(4):541–552.
- Mazenc, F. and Malisoff, M. (2017). Stabilization and robustness analysis for time-varying systems with time-varying delays using a sequential subpredictors approach. *Automatica*, 82:118–127.
- Middleton, R. H. and Miller, D. E. (2007). On the achievable delay margin using LTI control for unstable plants. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, 52(7):1194–1207.
- Mondié, S. and Michiels, W. (2003). Finite spectrum assignment of unstable time-delay systems with a safe implementation. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, 48(12):2207–2212.
- Nicaise, S., Valein, J., and Fridman, E. (2009). Stability of the heat and of the wave equations with boundary time-varying delays. *Discrete and Continuous Dynamical Systems - Series S*, 2(3):559.
- Pila, A., Shaked, U., and de Souza, C. E. (1999). H_∞ filtering for continuous-time linear systems with delay. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, 44(7):1412–1417.
- Rugh, W. J. and Shamma, J. S. (2000). Research on gain scheduling. *Automatica*, 36(10):1401–1425.
- Sanz, R., Garcia, P., and Krstic, M. (2018). Robust compensation of delay and diffusive actuator dynamics without distributed feedback. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAC.2018.2887148>.
- Selivanov, A. and Fridman, E. (2016). Observer-based input-to-state stabilization of networked control systems with large uncertain delays. *Automatica*, 74:63–70.
- Smyshlyaev, A. and Krstic, M. (2004). Closed-form boundary state feedbacks for a class of 1-D partial integro-differential equations. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, 49(12):2185–2202.
- Smyshlyaev, A. and Krstic, M. (2005). Backstepping observers for a class of parabolic PDEs. *Systems & Control Letters*, 54(7):613–625.
- Song, X., Park, J. H., and Yan, X. (2017). Linear estimation for measurement-delay systems with periodic coefficients and multiplicative noise. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, 62(8):4124–4130.
- Van Assche, V., Dambrine, M., Lafay, J.-F., and Richard, J.-P. (1999). Some problems arising in the implementation of distributed-delay control laws. In *Decision and Control, 1999. Proceedings of the 38th IEEE Conference on*, volume 5, pages 4668–4672. IEEE.
- Watanabe, K. and Ito, M. (1981). An observer for linear feedback control laws of multivariable systems with multiple delays in controls and outputs. *Systems & control letters*, 1(1):54–59.
- Zhang, X.-M. and Han, Q.-L. (2008). Robust H_∞ filtering for a class of uncertain linear systems with time-varying delay. *Automatica*, 44(1):157–166.
- Zhong, Q.-C. (2004). On distributed delay in linear control laws-part i: discrete-delay implementations. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, 49(11):2074–2080.
- Zhou, B. (2016). On asymptotic stability of linear time-varying systems. *Automatica*, 68:266–276.
- Zhou, B., Li, Z.-Y., and Lin, Z. (2013). Observer based output feedback control of linear systems with input and output delays. *Automatica*, 49(7):2039–2052.

A Proof of Theorem 3

Let us define the errors

$$\tilde{X}(t) = X(t) - \hat{X}(t) \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$\tilde{u}(x, t) = u(x, t) - \hat{u}(x, t). \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Differentiating (A.1)-(A.2) and using (7)-(10) and (12)-(14), the error system is obtained as

$$\dot{\tilde{X}}(t) = A(t)\tilde{X}(t) - \dot{\phi}(t)\Phi(t, \phi)L(\phi)\tilde{u}(0, t), \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{u}_t(x, t) &= \pi(x, t)\tilde{u}_x(x, t) \\ &\quad - \dot{\phi}(t)C(\varphi)\Phi(\varphi, \phi)L(\phi)\tilde{u}(0, t), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$\tilde{u}(1, t) = C(t)\tilde{X}(t). \quad (\text{A.5})$$

To proceed, let us recall the following properties of the state transition matrix

$$\Phi(t, t) = I, \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$\Phi_t(t, \tau) = A(t)\Phi(t, \tau), \quad (\text{A.7})$$

$$\Phi_\tau(t, \tau) = -\Phi(t, \tau)A(\tau), \quad (\text{A.8})$$

$$\Phi(t_2, t_0) = \Phi(t_2, t_1)\Phi(t_1, t_0). \quad (\text{A.9})$$

Using (A.7)-(A.8), the following expressions can be obtained

$$\Phi_x(\varphi, t) = \varphi_x(x, t)A(\varphi)\Phi(\varphi, t), \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$\Phi_t(\varphi, t) = \varphi_t(x, t)A(\varphi)\Phi(\varphi, t) - \Phi(\varphi, t)A(t), \quad (\text{A.11})$$

where the chain differentiation rule was employed. Furthermore, evaluating (A.11) at $x = 0$ and using that $\varphi(0, t) = \phi(t)$ yields

$$\Phi_t(\phi, t) = \dot{\phi}(t)A(\phi)\Phi(\phi, t) - \Phi(\phi, t)A(t). \quad (\text{A.12})$$

The expressions derived above will be used to prove that the following transformation

$$\tilde{Z}(t) = \Phi(\phi(t), t)\tilde{X}(t), \quad (\text{A.13})$$

$$\tilde{w}(x, t) = \tilde{u}(x, t) - C(\varphi(x, t))\Phi(\varphi(x, t), t)\tilde{X}(t), \quad (\text{A.14})$$

maps (A.3)-(A.5) into the exponentially stable target system

$$\dot{\tilde{Z}}(t) = \dot{\phi}(t)F_1(\phi)\tilde{Z}(t) - \dot{\phi}(t)L(\phi)C(\phi)\tilde{w}(0, t), \quad (\text{A.15})$$

$$\tilde{w}_t(x, t) = \pi(x, t)\tilde{w}_x(x, t), \quad (\text{A.16})$$

$$\tilde{w}(1, t) = 0, \quad (\text{A.17})$$

where $F_1(t)$ was defined in Assumption 2. The time derivative of (A.13) is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\tilde{Z}}(t) &= \Phi_t(\phi, t)\tilde{X}(t) + \Phi(\phi, t)\dot{\tilde{X}}(t) \\ &= \dot{\phi}(t)A(\phi)\tilde{Z}(t) - \dot{\phi}(t)L(\phi)\tilde{u}(0, t) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.18})$$

where (A.3), (A.6), (A.9) and (A.12) were employed in the second row. Evaluating (A.14) at $x = 0$ and using (A.13) yields

$$\tilde{u}(0, t) = \tilde{w}(0, t) + C(\phi)\tilde{Z}(t),$$

which can be plugged into (A.18), leading to (A.15). On the other hand, computing the spatial and temporal derivatives of (A.14) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{w}_t(x, t) &= \pi(x, t)\tilde{w}_x(x, t) + \dot{\phi}(t)\Phi(\varphi, \phi)L(\phi)\tilde{u}(0, t) \\ &\quad - \varphi_t C'(\varphi)\Phi(\varphi, t)\tilde{X}(t) - C(\varphi)\Phi_t(\varphi, t)\tilde{X}(t) \\ &\quad - C(\varphi)\Phi(\varphi, t)[A(t)\tilde{X}(t) \\ &\quad - \dot{\phi}(t)\Phi(t, \phi)L(\phi)\tilde{u}(0, t)], \\ \tilde{w}_x(x, t) &= \tilde{u}_x(x, t) - \varphi_x C'(\phi)\Phi(\varphi, t)\tilde{X}(t) \\ &\quad - C(\phi)\Phi(\varphi, t)\tilde{X}(t), \end{aligned}$$

and thus one can see that (A.16) holds if

$$\begin{aligned} \pi(x, t)\varphi_x(x, t) - \varphi_t(x, t) &= 0, \\ \pi(x, t)\Phi_x(\varphi, t) - \Phi_t(\varphi, t) - \Phi(\varphi, t)A(t) &= 0, \\ \Phi(\varphi, \phi) - \Phi(\varphi, t)\Phi(t, \phi) &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

The first identity is readily verified from (6) and (11). Plugging (A.10)-(A.11) into the left side of the second identity yields $(\pi(x, t)\varphi_x(x, t) - \varphi_t(x, t))A(\varphi)\Phi(\varphi, t)$, which is zero provided that so is the term in brackets. The last identity follows from the property (A.9). Finally, evaluating (A.14) at $x = 1$ and using (A.5), one can see that (A.17) holds if $\Phi(\varphi(1, t), t) = I$, which follows from the fact that $\varphi(1, t) = t$ and the property (A.6).

Then, the (invertible) transformation (A.13)-(A.14) maps the error system (A.3)-(A.5) into the target system (A.15)-(A.17), which is next proved to be exponentially stable. Let us consider the functional

$$V_1(t) = \int_0^1 e^{bx} |\tilde{w}(x, t)|^2 dx. \quad (\text{A.19})$$

The time-derivative of (A.19) along the trajectories of (A.4)-(A.5) is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_1(t) &= \int_0^1 2e^{bx} \pi(x, t) \tilde{w}(x, t)^T \tilde{w}_x(x, t) dx \\ &= -\pi(0, t) |\tilde{w}(0, t)|^2 - \int_0^1 \sigma(x, t) e^{bx} |\tilde{w}(x, t)|^2 dx, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.20})$$

where integration by parts was applied and $\sigma(x, t) = b\pi(x, t) + \pi_x(x, t)$. Observe that

$$\pi(0, t) = \frac{\dot{\phi}(t)}{t - \phi(t)}, \quad (\text{A.21})$$

and

$$\sigma(x, t) = \frac{1 + (b-1)\dot{\phi}(t) - bx(\dot{\phi}(t) - 1)}{t - \phi(t)}, \quad (\text{A.22})$$

which follow from (11). From (A.21), one has that

$$\pi(0, t) \geq \frac{c_1}{D}. \quad (\text{A.23})$$

On the other hand, since (A.22) is a linear function of x , its minimum occurs either at $x = 0$ or $x = 1$, and thus

$$\sigma(x, t) \geq \min\left\{\frac{1 + (b-1)\dot{\phi}(t)}{t - \phi(t)}, \frac{1 - \dot{\phi}(t) + b}{t - \phi(t)}\right\}. \quad (\text{A.24})$$

Choosing $b \geq \max\{1, c_2\}$ in (A.24), yields

$$\sigma(x, t) \geq \frac{\beta^*}{D}, \quad (\text{A.25})$$

with $\beta^* = \min\{1 + (b-1)c_1, 1 - c_2 + b\} > 0$, and thus plugging (A.23) and (A.25) into (A.20) leads to

$$\dot{V}_1(t) \leq -\frac{c_1}{D}|\tilde{w}(0, t)|^2 - \frac{\beta^*}{D} \int_0^1 e^{bx} |\tilde{w}(x, t)|^2 dx. \quad (\text{A.26})$$

Now, let us look at the Lyapunov function

$$V_2(t) = \tilde{Z}(t)^T W_1(\phi(t)) \tilde{Z}(t), \quad (\text{A.27})$$

whose derivative along the trajectories of (A.15) can be bounded, using Young's inequality, by

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_2(t) &= \dot{\phi}(t) \tilde{Z}^T (W_1(\phi) F_1(\phi) + F_1^T(\phi) W_1(\phi) \\ &\quad + \dot{W}_1(\phi)) \tilde{Z} + 2\dot{\phi}(t) \tilde{Z}^T W_1(\phi) L(\phi) C(\phi) \tilde{w}(0, t) \\ &\leq -c_1 q_1 |\tilde{Z}|^2 + 2c_2 \tau_1 |\tilde{Z}| |\tilde{w}(0, t)| \\ &\leq -\frac{c_1 q_1}{2} |\tilde{Z}|^2 + \frac{2c_2^2 \tau_1^2}{c_1 q_1} |\tilde{w}(0, t)|^2, \quad \forall t \geq t_0, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.28})$$

where $\tau_1 = \|W_1(t) L(t) C(t)\|_\infty$, Assumptions 1-2 were used and $q_1 > 0$ is defined such that $Q(t) \geq q_1 I$, $\forall t \geq \phi(t_0)$. Let us choose now

$$V_0(t) = \frac{2\bar{D}c_2^2\tau_1^2}{c_1^2q_1} V_1(t) + V_2(t), \quad (\text{A.29})$$

whose derivative can be bounded using (A.26) and (A.28) by

$$\dot{V}_0(t) \leq -\frac{c_1 q_1}{2} |\tilde{Z}|^2 - \frac{2\beta^* c_2^2 \tau_1^2}{c_1^2 q_1} \int_0^1 e^{bx} |\tilde{w}(x, t)|^2 dx, \quad (\text{A.30})$$

for all $t \geq t_0$. From (A.29)-(A.30), one has that $\dot{V}_0(t) \leq -\mu V_0(t)$, $\forall t \geq t_0$ and thus, by the comparison principle,

$$V_0(t) \leq e^{-\mu(t-t_0)} V_0(t_0), \quad (\text{A.31})$$

where $\mu = \min\left\{\frac{c_1 q_1}{2w_2}, \frac{\beta^*}{D}\right\}$, and $w_1, w_2 > 0$ are defined such that $w_1 I \leq W_1(t) \leq w_2 I$. Let us denote $\Xi(t) = |\tilde{Z}(t)|^2 + \int_0^1 \tilde{w}^2(x, t) dx$. The following relation holds

$$\psi_1 \Xi(t) \leq V_0(t) \leq \psi_2 \Xi(t), \quad (\text{A.32})$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_1 &= \min\left\{w_1, \frac{2\bar{D}c_2^2\tau_1^2}{c_1^2q_1}\right\}, \\ \psi_2 &= \max\left\{w_2, \frac{2\bar{D}c_2^2\tau_1^2 e^b}{c_1^2q_1}\right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, using (A.31) and (A.32) yields

$$\Xi(t) \leq \frac{\psi_2}{\psi_1} e^{-\mu(t-t_0)} \Xi(t_0), \quad \forall t \geq t_0. \quad (\text{A.33})$$

Let us denote $\Upsilon(t) = |X(t)|^2 + \int_0^1 \tilde{u}(x, t) dx$ and write the inverse of (A.13)-(A.14) as

$$\tilde{X}(t) = \Phi(t, \phi(t)) \tilde{Z}(t), \quad (\text{A.34})$$

$$\tilde{u}(x, t) = \tilde{w}(x, t) + C(\varphi(x, t)) \Phi(\varphi(x, t), \phi(t)) \tilde{Z}(t). \quad (\text{A.35})$$

From (A.13)-(A.14) and (A.34)-(A.35), one can show that there exist $\rho_1, \rho_2 > 0$ such that

$$\rho_1 \Upsilon(t) \leq \Xi(t) \leq \rho_2 \Upsilon(t), \quad (\text{A.36})$$

and thus the exponential stability estimate

$$\Upsilon(t) \leq \frac{\rho_2}{\rho_1} \frac{\psi_2}{\psi_1} e^{-\mu(t-t_0)} \Upsilon(t_0), \quad \forall t \geq t_0,$$

follows from (A.33) and (A.36), which completes the proof. \square